

Obedient-Disobedient Behaviour and Emotional Stability with Gender of Adolescent Student

Dr. Zunjarrao S. Kadam

Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Yashwantrao Chavan Mahavidyalaya Pachwad Tal: Wai,
Dist. Satara 415513 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: drzunjarkadam@gmail.com

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Abstract

Adolescence is the most important period in the development from child to adult. Family activity, educational responsibility and social interaction increases during this developmental stage. Which increases an emotional and psychological pressure that can reflect as mental health issues. Emotional stability refers to a person's ability to remain stable and balanced in any situation, it is a direct contributor to happiness and living the good life. It is a desirable trait, which can withstand difficult situations and handle adversity, remain productive and capable whatever be the situation.

Adolescent's emotional stability is a key component and a consistent predictor of healthy psychosocial development, lower levels of problem behavior, and positive developmental outcomes. Emotional disability reflects as adolescent's obedient and disobedient behavior and create sadness, loss of interest or pleasure, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, feelings of tiredness, and poor concentration.

Keywords: Obedient, Disobedient, Emotional behavior

Introduction

Adolescence is a period of development from childhood to adulthood. This period is characterized by physical, cognitive, socio-emotional and contextual changes (Steinberg et al. 2002). It is a personality development period, in this duration the adolescents acquire sexual maturity, hormonal change and pursuits, and establishes an identity as an individual apart from the family. This period is said to be the spring of life and an important era in the total life span (Parker & Benson, 2004). The World Health Organization gives a definition of adolescence as "the period in human growth and development that occurs after childhood and before adulthood" and consider this to be the period between the ages of 10 years to 19 years of age, which accounts approximately 17% of the world's population (WHO, 2015). In this period family activity, educational responsibility and social interaction increases its pressure on adolescents, which can result in

mental health issues such as emotional disability. Which usually result in weaker academic results and delinquent behavior in the adolescents. For most adolescents, this transition works out smoothly and without any larger problems. Mostly, adolescents adjust well to the “growing up challenge”, but for some adolescents this time is a difficult one. It is a time of psychological problems, a time with severe conflicts in the relations with the adult world and even with their peers. These types of problem are often called behavioral problems. **Collins & Steinberg, (2006)** emphasized the delinquent behavior is one of the most suffering problems during the period of adolescence ages. According to **Griffin et. Al. (2000), Elliott, Huizinga and Menard (2012)**, the list of delinquent activities include negative response to adhere the parental demands, stealing, property destruction, alcohol use, drug addiction and rape etc. it is a fact, that opinion regarding the causes of delinquent behavior vary, but it is generally agreed that delinquent behavior in adolescent years is more common. Obedience is generally distinguished as compliance and disobedience is a behavioral noncompliance. Emotional stability is a desirable trait, without it we risk falling into a pattern of jealousy, stress, headache and depression. It means one can withstand difficult situations handle adversity and remain productive and capable throughout. Emotional stability is not only one of the effective determinants of the personality patterns but it also helps to control the growth of adolescent development. Emotionally stable person knows how to face reality. They realize their limitations; this restricts them from acute frustration. Emotionally stable person is capable of confronting frustrating situations, they given no impulsive or immediate reactions. This is a sign of maturity such persons do not move or shift rapidly form one state of emotion to another. They try to check or hold their emotion before expressing of them. Delaying emotional responses depends on person’s ability to control his emotions (**Kaur, 2013; Basu, 2012; Aleem, 2005; Hay and Ashman, 2003**). According to **Kumar (2012)** “Adolescents who are emotionally and mentally healthy have the tools for coping with difficult situations and creative in bad times as well as good”. Counseling programme among adolescents improve self-confidence and emotional stability and relationship between happiness and extraversion in relation to obedient and disobedient behavior. Findings suggest that the emotionally stable adolescents show obedient behavior (**Gumora and Arseni, 2002; Hills and Argyle, 2001; Vishal & Kaji, 2014; Blanty, 2004; Sharma, 2006**). **Roul & Bihari (2016)** revealed that the positive association exists between components of emotional stability, parental support, obedient behavior and happiness among young adolescents.

Objectives of The Study

The objectives of the present study are as under:

To examine the role of emotional stability on obedient and disobedient behavior showing by adolescents.

To study the differences, if any, in gender in terms of emotional stability of obedient and disobedient adolescents.

Hypotheses

Taking into account the aims and objective of the investigation, the following hypothesis were framed for verification:

There will be a significant difference between obedient and disobedient adolescents on emotional stability.

There will be no significant difference between the two groups of boy students showing obedient and disobedient behavior on emotional stability.

There will be significant difference between the two groups of girl students showing obedient and disobedient behavior on emotional stability.

The different theoretical bases were accorded to justify the tenability of the hypothesis framed for verification.

Method

Present study is a type of survey research and is based on random sampling. With respect to this research, the researcher has used suitable methodology and planned an appropriate research design, Following are the points involved in the research methodology:

The purpose of the present research was to study how emotional stability and disability affects the behavior of adolescents.

Sample

For the present research 200 participants were randomly selected from the student's population studying in different Secondary and higher secondary schools of Satara and Karad Districts of Satara of class VIII, X, XI and XII adolescent students were included in the sample. The age range of the participants varied from 12 to 19. Participants were further classified on the basis of scores obtained on obedient disobedient tendency scale (obedient 100 and disobedient 100).

Tools

The following tools were used in the present study:

- Obedient Disobedient Tendency Scale (ODTS).
- Emotional Stability Scale by Gupta and Singh (1985)
- Self-made Personal Data Sheet was used to gather detailed information about the subject related to their caste, family, income etc.

Results and Discussion

Here we have applied Obedient Disobedient Tendency Scale and selected 100 each obedient and disobedient adolescents and then applied Emotional Stability Scale for obtaining the result.

Table 1: Mean, SD & t-ratior of Emotional Stability of Obedient and Disobedient Adolescents

Adolescents Group	No.	Mean	SD	t-ratio	p value
Obedient	100	8.21	2.10	3.41	<.01
Disobedient	100	7.03	2.75		

Table 1 reveals that the Mean score of obedient adolescents is higher (8.21) than their counterparts (7.03) on the measure of Emotional Stability, mean difference is also significant as t-ratio ($t = 3.41, p < .01$) is significant beyond .01 of level of significance. According to **Borrilla (1999); Lorenzo (2000); Hills and Argyle (2001)**, the emotional stability has relationship between obedient and disobedient behavior, the emotionally stable adolescents show obedient behavior. Therefore, our first hypothesis supported through obtained result.

Table 2: Mean, SD & t-ratior of Emotional Stability of Obedient and Disobedient Adolescents (Boys)

Adolescents Boys	No.	Mean	SD	t-ratio	p value
Obedient	100	8.03	2.05	5.57	<.01
Disobedient	100	6.01	2.99		

Table 2 reveals that the Mean score of obedient Boys is higher (8.03) than their disobedient adolescent counterparts (6.01) on the measure of Emotional Stability. Mean difference is also significant as t-ratior ($t=5.57, p < .01$) is significant beyond .01 of level of significance. **Moitra and Mukherjee (2012)** argued that male adolescents show significant value of emotional stability on obedient-disobedient behavior. Therefore, our second hypothesis supported through obtained result and previous studies.

Table 3: Mean, SD & t-ratio of Emotional Stability of Obedient and Disobedient Adolescents (Girls).

Adolescents Girls	No.	Mean	SD	t-ratio	p value
Obedient	100	7.99	1.99	7.94	<.01
Disobedient	100	5.74	2.02		

Table-3 reveals that the Mean score of obedient adolescent Girls is higher (7.99) than their disobedient counterparts (5.74) on the measure of Emotional Stability. Mean difference is also significant as *t*-ratio ($t = 7.94, p < .01$) is significant beyond .01 of level of significance. Therefore, our third hypothesis supported through obtained result. **Susan (2004) and Aleem (2005)** Found that the prevalence of emotional stability among male and female adolescent students and their mean scores showed that male students found to be more emotionally stable than female students.

Conclusion

Obedience and disobedience are generally distinguished as compliance and non-compliance behaviour of adolescents. Emotional Stability refers to a person's ability to remain stable and balanced; it is a direct contributor to happiness and living the good life. Emotionally stable adolescents face society in a better way. They emotionally adjust themselves and behaves according socially acceptable manners. When adolescents face difficulties in coping up in their family environment, school or study and society, they become emotionally imbalance. Comparative studies on obedient and disobedient behavior have observed that males are more disobedient than females (**Kalhotra & Sharma, 2013; Griffin et. al., 2000; Gumora, 2002**). **Hay and Ashman (2003)** study reflect the gender differences are associated with the development of adolescents' sense of general self-concept and emotional stability among adolescents. **Lounsbury et al. (2005); Date (2006)** both the boys and men were more emotionally stable than girls and women. In our research we also found that adolescent's rearing practices adopted by parents supports their obedient disobedient behavior and emotional stability. Adolescent boys were more emotionally stable in comparison to adolescent girls, because girls have a nature to attach the situation emotionally. If the situation changed or unfavorable they feel difficulty in handing it, they become imbalance or emotionally unstable.

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